

ASSESSMENT OF WOMEN'S OPINION ABOUT THE RISK LEVEL OF OVERWEIGHT AND OBESITY

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Abstract: In this article, we will determine the concept of overweight and obesity levels among women, and determine which levels of obesity are common among women, and which stages of obesity levels meet in women. Determining the frequency of additional comorbid diseases as a result of obesity. The causes of obesity in women are studied and analyzed statistically. The order in which diseases occur in women and men and their percentages, statistics of changes in obesity depending on age and gender are considered.

Key words: obesity, risk levels, statistics, comorbidity, Kettle index and cardiovascular system, age-related changes, gender, abdominal obesity, abdominal circumference.

Аннотация: В этой статье мы определим понятие избыточного веса и уровня ожирения среди женщин, а также определим, какие уровни ожирения распространены среди женщин и какие стадии ожирения встречаются у женщин. Определение частоты дополнительных коморбидных заболеваний вследствие ожирения. Причины ожирения у женщин изучены и проанализированы статистически. Рассмотрены порядок возникновения заболеваний у женщин и мужчин и их процентное соотношение, статистика изменения ожирения в зависимости от возраста и пола.

Ключевые слова: ожирение, уровни риска, статистика, коморбидность, индекс Кеттла и сердечно-сосудистая система, возрастные изменения, пол, абдоминальное ожирение, окружность живота.

Purpose of work. Exploring women's perceptions of overweight (BMI) and obesity risk as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Implementation of measures to prevent diseases caused by obesity among women and the population. Learning how to prevent obesity and excess body weight

body mass index is a quantity that allows to assess the level of compatibility of a person's height and weight, and is used to determine whether he is underweight, normal or overweight. Obesity (Latin. Adipositas - obesity and obesity - fullness, fatness, fattening) is the result of the formation of excess fat deposits that can be harmful to health. Obesity in adults corresponds to a body mass index (BMI) of 30.

In addition to obesity, experts distinguish overweight as a result of the formation of abnormal body fat with a BMI $\geq$ 25 (in adults). Overweight and obesity in children are determined separately for the 0-5 and 5-19 age groups according to deviations from the standard indicators of physical development of children accepted by the WHO. Overweight and obesity-related diseases cause great economic damage and are a factor that reduces labor productivity.

There are different forms of obesity in women and men.

Central obesity is an excess of body fat in the abdominal cavity. Central obesity is the most dangerous form of obesity and is statistically associated with an increased risk of heart disease, high blood pressure, and diabetes mellitus. Abdominal obesity is more common in men than in women. In women, it occurs when many branches of metabolism are disturbed.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted among 108 women. Metabolic syndrome (MS) is diagnosed in the presence of abdominal obesity (AO) - waist circumference > 94 cm for men and > 80 cm for women. BMI was calculated according to the formula: weight (kg) / height (m)², ≥ 25 and IC levels ≥ 30 are considered obese. Results. When examining AO, BMI, and cardiovascular risk in obese women, less than half (43.84%) of all women surveyed considered abdominal obesity to be a significant risk factor for CVD. At the same time, every fifth woman (19.96%) does not consider AO to be a risk factor for CVD. Only 2/5 of women with AO recognize obesity as a serious risk factor for CVD (41.01%), and 44.79% of respondents answered that obesity is not a very important risk factor.

Next, BMI and risk estimates were analyzed among obese women. It was found that only half of obese women (52.94%) and 2/5 of women with BMI (42.11%) considered obesity to be a significant risk factor for CVD. Almost every third woman with BMI (35.96%) and obesity (30.39%) does not believe that weight gain significantly increases cardiovascular risk. 21.93% of women with BMI and 16.67% of obese women did not consider their weight gain to be a risk factor for CVD.

Summary. Thus, an awkward situation arose among the female population regarding the assessment of their body weight and the importance of increased weight in the formation of hearts. The fact that excess body weight in women in many cases depends on the state of working conditions and eating habits, and the cases where these cases occur knowingly by women make up a large percentage. In women, all three levels of obesity are not equally distributed, and the risk factors are similarly high in some populations, although the risk factors and comorbidities are much less percentages. We can see that even if obesity is 1 degree in women working in a certain profession, several comorbid conditions occur at the same time.

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